

WILL – WELLBEING INITIATIVE FOR LEARNING AND LIVING

HOW CAN STRATEGIC DESIGN HELP CHRONIC DISEASE PATIENTS MANAGE THEIR HEALTH AND WELLBEING?

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ABSTRACT

Chronic diseases are considered the epidemic of the 21st century. Present healthcare systems are weak in coordination and communication to address chronic conditions since they were not designed for such purpose. Chronic diseases are difficult to manage, making daily life a challenge for patients. With the purpose of addressing “How strategic design can help chronic disease patients manage their health and wellbeing,” WILL (Wellbeing Initiative for Learning & Living) designed a model using strategic design, design thinking and Triple Bottom Line by Design plus Culture (TBLD+C) framework. Strategic design contributes to the application of traditional design principles to create more resilient and durable solutions, design thinking adds the human-centered approach and TBLD+C provide a combined understanding of People-Planet-Profit accompanied by Culture. The intent was to design a patient-centered innovation that engages all stakeholders and empowers patients to manage their diseases. Overall, WILL aims to develop a strategic care management system to propel a movement in health and wellbeing industries towards improving patients’ quality of life.

KEYWORDS: *Chronic Disease Management | Wellbeing and Quality of Life | Strategic Design | Design Thinking*

INTRODUCTION

“The growing number of persons suffering from major chronic illnesses face many obstacles in coping with their condition, not least of which is medical care that often does not meet their needs for effective clinical management, psychological support, and information” (Wagner, et al, 2001, pg. 1). Chronic diseases (Non Communicable Diseases or NCDs) progress slowly and may last indefinitely while limiting productivity, independence and decreasing quality of life in the process (Institute of Medicine, 2012). Thus, the patients’ lives change irreversibly with their changing medical conditions.

Different models of care have been designed revealing the need for a multidisciplinary approach to treating NCDs. These models are based on the general principle that the patient’s involvement and ability to manage the condition is indispensable for the overall success of the treatment’. Still, these models have not been planned to be adaptable to different environmental settings (e.g. patient’s access to healthy foods, usual source of care, and to technology).

WILL is a strategic design program whose purpose is to drive social innovation by adapting healthcare services to optimize resources within communities. In the case of NCDs, WILL proposes a model formulated from the basis of design and strategic thinking. This model is intended to be adaptable for the community involved, taking into account available resources, access to technology, and the specific characteristics of the disease.

CHRONIC DISEASE OVERVIEW

NCDs are long-lasting conditions that may be controlled but not cured and affect the population worldwide (Center for Managing Chronic Disease, n.d.). Heart disease, cancer, diabetes and autoimmune conditions are examples of NCDs that account for a substantial health burden globally (World Health Organization, 2005a).

Ironically, NCDs are among the most common and high-cost health conditions, but they are also among the most prevent-

able, and a majority of them can be effectively controlled (Center for Managing Chronic Disease, n.d.). NCDs have great impact due to: unfavorable effects on quality of life, causing premature death, and causing high, underappreciated economic burden for individuals, families, and communities (World Health Organization, 2005b).

NCDs cause recurrent disability at different levels often for decades or long periods. The most common measurement used to calculate this burden is the Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALYs). DALYs are a combination of years lost due to premature death and time spent in less than full health. Around 86% of DALYs correspond to people under the age of 70 with approximately 16 million deaths per year of people in this age group (World Health Organization, 2005b).

Furthermore, the economic liability that NCDs represent is unsustainable. In the US, NCDs contribute 75% of the \$2 trillion invested in annual healthcare (Institute of Medicine, 2012). Adding the economic implications of premature death, DALYs, and expenses for health care, treatment and secondary consequences of the illness; NCDs consequently pose a major concern for overall community productivity.

CURRENT SITUATION

Although genetics and aging influence the predisposition of individuals to NCDs, environmental factors, extending from pollutant exposure, to lower socioeconomic circumstances (e.g., poor diet or lack of access to healthcare services) have a considerable and unavoidable impact on the incidence and development of NCDs (Sears & Genuis, 2012).

General treatment and research on NCDs has mostly failed at understanding the big picture with a systematic approach to these conditions, many of which can be associated with unhealthy diet, stress, lack of physical activity, improper housing, daily exposure to toxins, etc. given that such circumstances are mostly related to low socioeconomic status, NCDs tend to be more problematic for low-income families (World Health Organization, 2005a; Sears & Genuis, 2012). Moreover, there are clear gaps in the general treatment for NCDs such as patients' understanding of the condition and management plan, lack of proper lifestyle and environmental conditions analysis, and deficiencies in multidisciplinary approaches (Harris & Zwar, 2007).

Care for NCD patients is not well organized because worldwide systems are not designed for these types of diseases. This results in overuse or underuse of services, unnecessary medical payments, and confusion due to opposite/conflicting advice from health care providers. Globally, healthcare systems need to undergo reforms to reshape the service for chronic care. The change should include training and education of care providers, communication protocols, support systems, and awareness campaigns among others (Anderson, 2010).

WINDOW OF OPPORTUNITY

The World Health Organization (2008) has defined prevention and control of NCDs as "Tackling the world's biggest killers and addressing key challenges to global development in the 21st century" (p. 5). Wagner, et al. (2001) rightfully stated, "High-quality NCD care is characterized by productive interactions between practice team and patients" (p. 68). Facilitating communication by providing opportunities for feedback from the patient, enabling the improved flow of messages between provider and patient, and supporting patients' self-management, is productive and effective when all actors are actively involved, informed, and prepared. Patients should be ready to take advantage of the treatment and guidance they receive to be engaged in improving their health and wellbeing (Wagner, Austin, et al., 2001).

There is a worldwide shortage of healthcare resources, specifically primary care providers and a supporting healthcare team, which limits access to primary health care. A coordinated and collaborative healthcare team is needed to supplement provision of the ongoing services needed by patients with NCDs.

The real challenge is how to combine and utilize the resources available and improve communication and information flow that can enable patients and doctors to be on the same page. Tools, resources and means developed around the actors should facilitate this process.

The constraints in the current system present a design opportunity. Since people suffering from NCDs will live with their condition throughout their entire lives, the goal of treatment and health services should focus on quality of life. By addressing pain management, continuous informed medical treatments, adjustment to the social and psychological burden, and use and accessibility of community resources, NCD patients will have a better quality of life and be better prepared to manage their conditions; enhancing productivity, independence and promoting collaborative management at the same time.

WHAT HAS BEEN DONE?

Different healthcare models have been designed to address NCD treatment. Most of them are developed with the purpose of empowering patients to self-manage their condition properly and leave the healthcare team as supporting actors. Several of these care management models are described below.

The Chronic Care Model (CCM) was developed for healthcare organizations as a guide to improve chronic care, especially for low-income populations (Wagner, et al., 2001). This model considers healthcare organizations, community resources, self-management support, delivery system design, decision support and clinical information systems with the intent to reinforce the patients' and their families' role in managing NCDs, help the patient set goals, identify barriers and plan

how to overcome the barriers in order to achieve the goals (Wagner, et al., 2001).

The Stepped Care Model presents a framework for professional support that is based on patients' responses to treatment (Von Korff & Tiemens, 2000), recognizing that all patients have different conditions and may require different levels of care. The purpose is to build a partnership with common goals and a care plan followed by active follow-up. As the patients move up each of the four levels, the collaborative management gets stronger, as it becomes more of a 'team task' (Von Korff & Tiemens, 2000).

Flinders Model allows doctors to develop collaborative care plans with their clients and to assess patients' self-management capabilities. They use "A number of standardized tools/forms: the Partners in Health Scale, Cue and Response Questionnaire, Problem and Goals, and Care Plan" (Victorian State Government, n.d., pg. 2).

To provide a basic protocol of how clinical teams should properly tend to chronic disease patients, the World Health Organization designed a five-step model (5As) with recommendations and tips to improve general treatment: Assess, Advise, Agree, Assist, Arrange. This model considers different variables that health providers should implement in order to establish suitable processes to treat NCD patients. For example, the use of neutral, common language when discussing diseases and treatments, assessing patient's goals, knowledge and beliefs before implementing a plan of action, and assisting with information, tools and follow ups.

All of these models were designed to include the patient in the management of their NCDs and a collaborative and coordinated healthcare team. However, they do not provide ongoing opportunities for the patient to provide feedback about what is working, and what is not working, including the challenges they face in their built and living environments to adhere to their care plans. Without this vital information, the provider cannot make adjustments to the care plan such as including nurse practitioners, physical therapists, nutritionists or other allied health professionals on the disease management team or provide alternative protocols to improve the patients' quality of life.

According to an initiative from the Victorian State Government (n.d.), "The best model is the one that meets the person's needs for self-management support; this will vary between people and at different times for any one individual" (pg. 3). The challenge relies on succeeding in designing the right intellectual and behavioral toolkit to produce an impact on the health and wellbeing industries since the existing models have not proven to be efficient enough when implemented in isolation (Australian Government Department of Health, n.d.). Different factors in the specific context must be considered to fully tackle the patient's needs. Adaptability and flexibility for a model to be implemented regardless the type of disease, the technological ability of patients, caregivers, and healthcare team, and the environmental settings surrounding implementation, are essential for the proper delivery of chronic disease care.

METHODOLOGY

Based on our literature review, we developed a model that addresses the gaps identified in the current models. We designed our model using strategic design, design thinking and the Triple Bottom Line by Design plus Culture (TBLD+C) framework. Strategic design contributes to the application of traditional design principles to create more resilient and durable solutions; design thinking adds the human-centered approach and TBLD+C provides a combined understanding of People-Planet-Profit accompanied by Culture. Our model is based on a strategic design system (Figure 1) intended to address chronic disease management. The patient is at the core and is directly influenced by his/her context, which includes his/her social core, healthcare team, the community, and the environment. Factors such as communication, education, feedback, and collaboration also impact the patient's health and wellbeing.

To formalize our model, we designed and conducted a survey of a broad sample of patients, providers and caregivers to identify the flow of information, gaps and barriers in the communication processes, contributions and influence of each actor, and opportunities and insights that should be part of the model being designed.

The questions were designed to gather information related to medication systems, socio-economic status, lifestyle (diet and exercise), appointments and follow-ups, and other general information relevant to improving the management of NCDs, as well as demographic and lifestyle information. The purpose was to better understand provider resources, the en-

Strategic Design System

Guidelines and principles for the design proposal

Adapted from Pediatric Patient-Centered Framework, 2014, Tahara & Laufer

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Figure 1. Strategic Design System

Country	# of Patients (N=197)	# of Doctors (N=53)	# of Caregivers (N=173)
India	109	5	115
Colombia	53	26	21
Turkey	35	22	37

Figure 2. Response Chart

environment in which the patients live, as well as personal factors (age, type of disease, economic status, etc.) and lifestyle factors (behaviors, environment, nutrition, exercise, etc.). All the information gathered enabled the research team to identify challenges, barriers, and breaches in the implementation of and adherence to care plans and opportunities to improve NCD management.

The surveys were translated into three different languages: Spanish, Turkish, and Marathi and were administered in Colombia, Turkey and India. These locations were selected for convenience reasons since members of the research team had access to healthcare facilities in the designated location and posed an opportunity to gather valuable information about how NCD management is addressed within different cultures including socio-economic differences.

Cross-cultural results revealed the un-tackled opportunity posed by engaging caregivers as key participants in patients' NCD management. For example in India, since many caregivers share the same household with patients, they have major involvement in their day-to-day activities, including those related to health and wellbeing.

Data also showed that different resources and access to technology confirm the need to have an adaptable and inclusive intervention model rather than a specific tool with exclusive requirements that targets a population with specific characteristics.

Lastly, providers manifested a concern regarding resources and means available to enhance communication due to time and human capital constraints. Additionally, results suggested that socio-economic status is related to healthcare literacy and it could be perceived that people with more financial resources among the survey participants, probably had better education compared to others. As a result, they have a better understanding of how to manage their condition and have a clear idea of how to approach communication with providers asking questions and researching their conditions. As this was a pilot study and used convenience sampling, more data will need to be gathered and analyzed to inform our design solution.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Design Management Program and faculty at Pratt Institute, Aditi Mukherjee, and Dr. Rodrigo Vargas.

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